

1 **Nestin, a disease modifying gene in human cancer, is associated with genetic background.**

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6 We previously demonstrated through comparison of total transcription (RNA) in primary tumors based on
7 race, using whole transcriptome technologies, that among the largest differences in the gene expression
8 of primary tumors of women with TNBC when compared based on race (genetic background) was nestin,
9 encoded by *NES*. Here, we compared total transcription (RNA) in the primary tumors based on
10 geographical origin of patient, examining the tumor transcriptome in black women from Africa or the
11 Americas, as well as whole genome methylation across transformation in black women with TNBC to
12 distinguish influences of genes and environment and further examine how nestin functions as a disease
13 (cancer) modifying gene in humans.
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Results

We previously found nestin among the genes most differentially expressed when comparing the primary tumors of women with TNBC based on race: primary tumors from white women with TNBC, and primary tumors from black women with TNBC. TNBC is described as having a more severe quality in black women, with time to disease progression one of these characteristics.

Epidemiologic studies have demonstrated that the risk of death from breast cancer increases when Japanese women migrate to the Americas, indicating environment interacts with genetics to influence disease outcomes in cancer. Thus, here we studied whole transcription in the primary tumors of black women with TNBC, from Africa and from the Americas, to distinguish contributions of the environment and genetics to TNBC disease severity in black women.

Figure 1: Nestin is among the genes whose expression is most different when comparing the transcriptomes of TNBC tumors from African Americans (black women from the United States) and Africans from Ghana and Ethiopia (black women from Africa)

GSE211167

n=17 African (*n*=11 Ethiopia and *n*=6 Ghana)

n=9 African-American

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10763	1.54E-04	0.571	3.784022	2.1607414	7934.59	NES	180/20897	99.1

Next, we compared total transcription in normal breast tissue based on race to distinguish the contributions determine if nestin differential expression observed in primary tumors of black and white women could be ascribed to normal gene expression in the breast or was a product of genetic background influence transformation resulting in nestin differential expression in black women with TNBC.

Figure 2: Nestin is not differentially expressed in normal breast tissue in black and white women.

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7921088	9.87e-01	0.0169597	-5.60923	0.00129674	NES	32978/33297	0.96

We also studied whole genome methylation (DNA; epigenetic modification) of normal breast tissue and tumor tissue in black women to identify, at the systems level and in an unbiased fashion, the most differentially methylated positions in the genome, examining epigenetic modification of the DNA during transformation from normal breast to breast tumor in black women.

1 **Figure 3:** A site in the Nestin coding sequence (the nestin gene) is among the most differentially
 2 methylated positions transcriptome-wide, when comparing normal tissues of the breast and primary
 3 tumors of the breast from black women.

4 GSE37754
 5 *n*=9 normal breast; African American women
 6 *n*=8 primary breast tumor; basal or TNBC subtype; African American women

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DM
cg04671462	2.85e-03	3.48	-1.6889482	5.32e-01	NES	30528/485577	93.7

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 8 **Discussion**

9 We demonstrated here that epigenetic modification of nestin changes significantly during
 10 transformation of the breast in black women, that methylation of a site in the coding region of nestin is
 11 nearly identical in white and black women, and that despite indications from the study of black and white
 12 women that nestin was a factor that influenced disease severity in TNBC derived from the genetic
 13 background, its expression was among those most different when comparing, indicating both environment
 14 and genetics contribute to the influence of nestin as a disease modifying gene in human cancer.

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Citations

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